

reddish brown margins and grey centers, or they may be greyish throughout, on the upper leaf sheath. Lower sheaths also are affected and superficial pink powdery growth of the fungus is visible on all the sheaths. Infection reaches the stem and causes browning and rotting of the peduncle. Panicles partially emerge or remain inside the sheath. Emerged panicles have chaffy grains or partially filled, thin grains.

During 1982 kharif, ShR caused losses of up to 50%. Incidence was greater in heavy soils where more nitrogen was applied or where *Trifolium alexandrinum* was sown in rabi.

In 1981 and 1982, *Fusarium equiseti* (Corda) Sacc. and *F. moniliforme* Sheld. were isolated from rice leaf sheaths.

Pathogenicity tests were performed to confirm their association with ShR and panicle sterility. Plants were inoculated by injecting conidial suspensions, or by

Fusarium sp. symptoms. on sheath after inoculation.

inserting mycelial bits grown on potato dextrose agar into the boot leaf sheath before panicle emergence. Typical symptoms (see figure) appeared with both

methods, lesions developed within 1 week, and the sheath rotted in 3 weeks. Both *Fusarium* species caused disease and produced identical symptoms. □

Effect of azolla on rice tungro virus disease

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Farmers have worried that rice crops that receive azolla to augment nitrogen supply are severely affected by tungro virus disease (RTV).

Seeds of TN1 and IR36 were sown, 5 seeds/pot, in pots containing 400 g soils with and without azolla. TN1 is susceptible to RTV and the RTV vector green leafhopper (GLH) *Nephotettix virescens*. IR36 is resistant to RTV in the field, moderately susceptible in the greenhouse, and moderately resistant

to GLH. Ten days after sowing, seedlings were exposed for 24 h to viruliferous GLH that had fed on diseased plants for 4 days. Inoculation was done in cages with 4-5 viruliferous insects per seedling. IR36 and TN1 seedlings raised with and without azolla were exposed separately and together. Uninoculated plants of the same age were kept as control.

The percentages of RTV-infected seedlings were recorded 12 days after inoculation and plant height was measured (Table 1).

Mean values of RTV-infected seedlings between plants raised with and without azolla were almost the same within varieties. TN1 was severely infected and IR36

was moderately infected.

About 500 viruliferous *N. virescens* adults and nymphs were released on pots containing azolla. No insect survived beyond 3 days. The *azolla* did not develop disease symptoms.

A field experiment was conducted in four 5 × 2 plots with wire mesh along the bunds to prevent azolla flow. Azolla (*A. pinnata* and *A. caroliniana*) was incorporated at 10 kg/plot. Fifteen days later, when fresh growth of azolla was seen, TN1 and IR36 seedlings raised in an insect-proof area were transplanted two plots per variety, one with azolla and the other without. Plant spacing was 20 × 15 cm. Leaf yellowing symptoms similar to RTV were noticed on some TN1 hills 15

Table 2. Average percentage of RTV-infected seedlings, and seedling height, IRRRI.^a

RTV-infected seedlings (%)				Height (cm) of infected seedlings				Height (cm) of uninfected seedlings			
IR36 A ⁺	IR36	TN1 A ⁺	TN1	IR36 A ⁺	IR36	TN1 A ⁺	TN1	IR36 A ⁺	IR36	TN1 A ⁺	TN1
—	—	76.67	94.17	—	—	22.68	20.42	—	—	39.83	36.44
—	—	100.00	100.00	—	—	—	—	—	—	—	—
42.50	—	75.00	—	26.80	—	27.14	—	42.70	—	44.88	—
50.00	45.00	90.00	88.90	29.70	27.30	25.33	30.82	43.56	34.35	44.45	38.45
57.50	—	82.50	—	29.00	—	28.19	—	42.00	—	32.64	—
—	—	93.25	81.25	—	—	27.25	24.81	—	—	46.33	35.67
33.33	47.06	—	—	31.69	32.64	—	—	35.83	37.24	—	—
45.00	42.00	80.00	82.35	31.93	29.40	30.11	28.35	44.86	36.05	46.25	39.10
45.67	44.69	85.35	89.33	29.82	29.78	26.78	26.10	41.79	35.88	42.39	37.42

^aA⁺ = raised with azolla.

Table 2. RTV-infected hills at different days after transplanting (DT).

Time of observation (DT)	RTV-infected hills (no.)			
	TN1		IR36	
	With azolla	Without azolla	With azolla	Without azolla
15	4.6	6.2	0	0
30	65.6	63.4	0.4	1.0
45	83.6	84.2	2.0	1.8

days after transplanting (DT). TN1 showed more than 80% infection 45 DT but IR36 remained almost disease free in both treatments (Table 2).

Results obtained in the greenhouse and in the field trial show that azolla application does not cause higher RTV incidence or render the resistant variety susceptible to RTV. □

The International Rice Research Newsletter (IRRN) invites all scientists to contribute concise summaries of significant rice research for publication. Contributions should be limited to one or two pages and no more than two short tables, figures, or photographs. Contributions are subject to editing and abridgement to meet space limitations. Authors will be identified by name, title, and research organization.

Biochemical properties of discolored rice grains

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The biochemical properties of discolored rice grains were analyzed and compared with those of healthy white grains (see table). Freshly harvested rice was dehusked and discolored grains were classified as brown, purple, or green. Associated fungi were isolated by blotter technique. Brown and purple grains yielded three species of fungi: *Helminthosporium oryzae*, *Trichoconis padwickii*, and *Curvularia lunata*. Green grains had *Helminthosporium oryzae*.

Brown grains had higher levels of phenol, reducing and nonreducing sugars, amylose, and gel consistency than white grains. Gelatinization score was lower than for normal grains. Brown grains contained glycine in addition to the eight other amino acids present in white grains.

Purple grains also had high levels of

Biochemical properties of discolored rice grains.

Property	Brown grain	Purple grain	Green grain	White (healthy)
Phenolic content (µg/g fresh wt)	260	56	65	50
Reducing sugar (µg/g fresh wt)	350	430	320	190
Nonreducing sugar (µg/g fresh wt)	1000	960	880	820
Percent amylose	9.4	8.0	7.6	8.8
Amino acids				
Isoleucine	+	+	+	+
Tryptophan	+	+	+	+
Tyrosine	+	+	+	+
Alanine	+	-	+	+
Aspartic acid	+	+	+	+
Glycine	+	+	+	-
Arginine	+	+	+	+
Histidine	+	+	+	+
Cystine	+	+	+	+
Gel consistency (mm)	147	123	96	119
Gelatinization	Intermediate	High or intermediate	High	low

phenol, reducing and nonreducing sugars, and gel consistency. Percent amylose and gelatinization were less than for healthy grains. Alanine, present in white grains, was not detectable, but purple grains,

contained glycine. Results for green grains were similar to those for brown grains, but brown grains contained more amylose and had higher gel consistency than other colored grains. □

Rice grain discoloration

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Rice grain discoloration reduces market value and consumption appeal and often is associated with pathogens. Pathogens that cause grain discoloration and the relationship between discoloration and weather factors were studied in Coimbatore, Tamil Nadu, India.

Seeds collected from mature panicles were dehusked and the discolored grains were classified as green, purple, or brown. Associated fungi were isolated by the blotter technique using 5,000 grains of

each calor. White grains (control) yielded no fungi. Green grains (0.8%) yielded *Helminthosporium oryzae*. Among the purple grains, 54.0% yielded *H. oryzae*, 12% yielded *Trichoconis padwickii*, and 5.0% yielded *Curvularia lunata*. Brown grains yielded 65.0, 8.0, and 3.0%, res-

pectively, of these fungi.

Panicles at the various stages of development in the field were inoculated by spraying a spore suspension (40,000 cells/ml) of the 3 species of fungi. Control plants were sprayed with water. The panicles were covered with paper bags im-

Table 1. Percentage of grains infected by the fungi.

Fungus species	Infected grains (%)			
	Flower	Milk	Soft dough	Dough
<i>H. oryzae</i>	26.5	21.5	5.9	0
<i>T. padwickii</i>	22.4	19.5	1.9	0
<i>C. lunata</i>	23.2	20.6	1.8	0
Control (water spray)	5.4	0	0	0